

The manosphere is political:

ideology, misogyny, and
attacks on gender policies

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Key Findings

→ **The Brazilian manosphere on Telegram is political.** More than 15,000 mentions of Lula and Bolsonaro alone were identified across the communities analyzed, tracking key moments in Brazil's national political context. These mentions, as well as the attacks and framings discussed in the report, appear across all five subcategories of communities examined (masculinist identities, masculinist self-improvement, misogyny, culture war, and cryptocurrencies and investments), indicating that politics cuts across the manosphere ecosystem broadly rather than being confined to groups explicitly devoted to political debate.

→ **These communities operate as spaces of ideological socialization.** Far from being limited to forums about relationships or masculinity, they function as environments for the circulation and consolidation of worldviews shaped by gender hierarchies, male victimhood, culture war, anti-leftism, and hostility to rights, organizing perceptions of authority, social order, public enemies, and the legitimacy of policies.

→ **Support for or rejection of political leaders is often mediated through the manosphere's own grammar.** Public figures are interpreted and evaluated through categories, values, and references typical of this universe, such as incel, honk pill, red pill, alpha male, or beta male. This shows that politics does not enter these groups merely as an external topic, but is filtered through a distinct language that reshapes perceptions of leadership, strength, decline, and legitimacy.

→ **Misogyny is articulated with other forms of hatred and can escalate into extreme discourse.** In the groups analyzed, sexism and misogyny are frequently intertwined with racism, classism, and LGBTphobia, reinforcing a hierarchical and exclusionary worldview. In its most extreme forms, this articulation reaches the normalization

and glorification of violence, as well as discourses of extermination and reproductive control.

→ **Gender policies are a recurring target of attack.** Rather than being debated as instruments of protection, prevention, or the guarantee of rights, agendas such as the Maria da Penha Law, sex education, and reproductive rights are frequently framed as threats to men, the family, and the moral order, or as evidence of a social order supposedly captured by feminism.

→ **Attacks on male politicians also extend to gender-based political violence directed at women associated with them,** such as wives or first ladies, who become recurring targets of insults, sexualized memes, and public humiliation. These attacks also mobilize and reveal the grammar of the manosphere insofar as they portray relations between men and women as a key lens through which to interpret status, success, power, and political legitimacy.

→ **The problem goes beyond online hate.** The communities analyzed do not simply disseminate misogynistic discourse; they also help produce and circulate frames that delegitimize public policies aimed at equality and protection, reinforcing a symbolic environment hostile to rights and conducive to the normalization of exclusion and violence.

Trigger Warning: *This report presents explicit examples of violence and hate speech related to gender, race, class, gender identity, and sexuality, including content that naturalizes, legitimizes, or incites sexual and physical violence. Including these materials seeks to make visible the concrete ways these attacks manifest in digital spaces, circulate across networks, and contribute to the normalization of violence, so as to support their identification, analysis, and confrontation.*

Executive Summary

This technical note shows that the Brazilian manosphere on Telegram should not be understood merely as a collection of misogynistic groups or “advice forums for men.” Rather, it constitutes a political space for the construction and circulation of ideology, in which misogyny organizes worldviews about authority, social order, merit, public enemies, and the legitimacy of rights. Drawing on a dataset of 85 Brazilian communities and more than 7 million pieces of content published between 2015 and 2025, the study combines quantitative and qualitative analysis to examine how politics appears in these communities and how they frame key issues on Brazil’s public agenda.

The findings show that the manosphere is political. The study identified 15,976 mentions of Lula and Bolsonaro across the communities analyzed, distributed across the five subcategories examined: masculinist identities, male self-improvement, misogyny, culture war, and cryptocurrencies and investments. This finding indicates that politics cuts across the manosphere ecosystem broadly, rather than being confined to groups explicitly devoted to political debate. At the same time, the qualitative analysis shows that this politicization goes beyond electoral preferences or support for specific leaders.

Mentions of ‘Bolsonaro’ and ‘Lula’ in Manosphere Communities (2016-2025)

What emerges is the circulation of a distinct ideology, marked by gender hierarchies, male victimhood, culture war, anti-leftism, anti-institutionalism, and hostility to rights, which in many respects converges with repertoires already identified in the literature on the Brazilian far right.

And this is only a small part of the total number of anti-male laws; being a man in Brazil is the status of a second-class citizen, and getting married makes you third-class.

Community in the category “Masculinist Identity” May/2025

In this sense, the manosphere operates as a space of ideological socialization. Misogyny does not appear as an isolated theme, but as an organizing axis of perceptions about who should exercise authority, who threatens the social order, and who may be treated as a legitimate enemy. Politics is filtered through its own grammar, in which public figures are interpreted through categories and references typical of this universe, such as incel, honk pill, red pill, alpha male, or beta male. This shows that the manosphere does not merely comment on national politics, but translates it into its own moral and affective repertoire, reshaping perceptions of leadership, strength, decline, and legitimacy. In this regard, we also observed content ridiculing politically visible women through sexual insults, public humiliation, and insinuations about their private behavior.

Maybe Lula has more control over that ugly Janja than Bolsonaro has over Michelle.

Community in the category “Masculinist Identity” August 2023

Attacks on women, feminists, LGBTQIA+ people, and other groups do not appear as marginal deviations or mere verbal excesses. The analysis also shows that misogyny rarely appears on its own: it is recurrently articulated with racism, classism, and LGBTphobia, reinforcing a broader logic of exclusion and dehumanization. In its most extreme forms, this articulation leads to the normalization and glorification of violence, as well as to discourses of extermination and reproductive control. The problem, therefore, is not limited to hostility toward women, but involves the production of broader moral and political enemies, in line with a political culture grounded in inequality, exclusion, and dehumanization.

One of the report’s central findings is that this ideology is also expressed through systematic attacks on gender policies. In the communities analyzed, issues such as the Maria da Penha Law, sex education, abortion, reproductive rights, and diversity are repeatedly framed as threats to men, the family, and social morality. Rather than being debated as public policies aimed at protection, prevention, or the guarantee of rights, these agendas are frequently presented as evidence of persecution against men, feminist capture of the state, and the moral decay of society. In this way, the manosphere does not merely express conservative positions: it helps produce a symbolic environment hostile to the legitimacy of public policies aimed at protection and gender equality.

The case of the Maria da Penha Law is particularly illustrative. In the content analyzed, the law appears less as an instrument to combat domestic violence than as a symbol of a legal system supposedly organized against men. It is associated with false accusations, loss of property, expulsion from the home, and the risks that heterosexual relationships allegedly pose to men. Something similar occurs with sex education, which is often framed as premature sexualization, indoctrination, and a threat to childhood, in strong articulation with the moral panic surrounding so-called “gender ideology.” Abortion, in turn, appears not as a matter of public

health or reproductive rights, but as a moral signifier that condenses several anxieties of this universe: antifeminism, anti-leftism, religious conservatism, conspiracy theories, and the dehumanization of the adversary. These framings show that the target of such discourses is not merely a specific policy, but the very idea of public policies aimed at equality and protection.

THE PENHA LIE MUST BE REPEALED.

Community in the category "Cryptocurrencies and investments", October/2025

From a public perspective, the report's main warning is that the manosphere should not be treated merely as a digital niche or an internet subculture. It operates as a space of ideological socialization, articulating humor, memes, resentment, culture war, and hostility to rights in highly adaptable ways. This helps explain why its repertoires can circulate easily between masculinist communities, political communities, and broader environments of radicalization. The problem, therefore, is not only the presence of misogyny online, but the way it organizes belonging, produces moral enemies, and contributes to eroding the legitimacy of gender-related public policies.

Ultimately, this technical note concludes that the Brazilian manosphere on Telegram should be understood as a political ecosystem of ideological construction, in which misogyny functions as an organizing axis of hierarchical and anti-egalitarian worldviews. By articulating culture war, male victimhood, dehumanization, and attacks on gender policies, these communities help reproduce a political culture hostile to equality and conducive to the normalization of violence, exclusion, and the erosion of rights. Addressing this phenomenon therefore requires more than monitoring misogynistic content: it requires understanding its connections to broader struggles over democracy, public values, and protection policies in contemporary Brazil.

1. Introduction

Gender inequalities are a structuring axis of power relations. In digital environments, they are increasingly articulated through highly connected misogynistic networks, a phenomenon the literature describes as the manosphere. The manosphere encompasses a constellation of communities, influencers, and discursive repertoires that produce and reproduce normative and hierarchical views of gender, often through humiliation, punitive “humor,” resentment, the inversion of oppression, and, in its most extreme forms, the normalization of violence and harassment against women.

In Brazil, recent evidence indicates that Telegram has become a strategic infrastructure for the reorganization of networks and communication strategies of far-right actors, fostering the intensive circulation of content in environments with low moderation and less public scrutiny. It is in this context that the Brazilian manosphere on Telegram finds particularly favorable conditions to expand, diversify its repertoires, and connect with other ideological agendas. Far from constituting merely a universe of male frustrations or debates about relationships, the Brazilian manosphere on Telegram should be understood as a political space in which misogyny is articulated with conservative values, hate speech, dehumanization of social groups, and the production of a hierarchical and anti-egalitarian worldview.

Building on our previous research on the Brazilian manosphere on Telegram (Ricard et al., 2025a) and in dialogue with the literature on conservative reaction and backlash against rights, this technical note advances a central hypothesis: the manosphere is political. More than an environment of misogynistic expression, it operates as an ecosystem of ideological socialization, in which discourses about masculinity, femininity, sexuality, and gender relations serve to engage, recruit, radicalize, and consolidate authoritarian and anti-egalitarian worldviews. In this process, misogyny does not appear as an isolated theme, but as a political grammar that organizes perceptions of authority, social order, public enemies, and the legitimacy of rights.

This politicization is not limited to electoral disputes or the circulation of content about leaders and parties. It also reaches the terrain of public policy.

In Telegram conspiracy communities, we have already analyzed discourses about the Maria da Penha Law (Alves et al., 2025a) and sex education (Alves et al., 2025b). Similarly, in the manosphere, these topics, alongside abortion, reproductive rights, and diversity, are frequently framed through moral panic, hostility toward feminism, and rhetorics of persecution against men. In this sense, the risk represented by the manosphere concerns not only political debate in the strict sense, but also the erosion of the legitimacy of public policies aimed at equality, equity, protection, and the expansion of rights.

This reading is close to arguments already developed in the literature on cultural and political backlash in Brazil, according to which civil society actors and networks not only dispute values and identities, but also act to block, delegitimize, or reverse public policies in the fields of gender, sexuality, reproduction, and ethnic-racial relations (Segatto et al., 2023). In the case of the manosphere, this process takes on its own characteristics: it combines informal language, humor, memes, pedagogies of resentment, and repertoires of digital culture with more explicit forms of attack on women, minorities, and equality agendas. Thus, the manosphere not only reflects existing political cleavages, but also helps reproduce a political culture hostile to rights and favorable to the naturalization of violence, hierarchy, and exclusion.

2. Background and Literature

Networks of hatred and violence against women, often described as the manosphere or masculinist sphere, have been analyzed as an expanding digital phenomenon that articulates misogyny, reactive masculinities, and online culture wars. In Brazil, Vilaça and d'Andréa (2021) show that the manosphere should not be read merely as a subculture about relationships or sexual frustrations, but as a field connected to the new right, the alt-right, and transnational repertoires such as the “red pill.” This literature suggests that the manosphere is political insofar as its discourses organize broader views about authority, hierarchy, social order, public enemies, and supposed male victimization.

The international literature reinforces this argument by pointing to a growing overlap between the manosphere and political ideologies. Mamié et al. (2021), for example, found evidence of audience convergence between antifeminist manosphere communities and the alt-right on platforms such as Reddit and YouTube. Similarly, Gottzén and Areschoug (2025) argue that

the manosphere has functioned as a space for shaping young male political subjectivities increasingly aligned with antifeminist and far-right ideologies. More than an episodic affinity, these studies suggest convergence around some central axes: defense of gender hierarchies, construction of moral and political enemies, antifeminist resentment, transgressive language, and legitimation of exclusion. In this sense, Preston et al. (2025) argue that misogyny and gender violence should not be treated as peripheral elements, but as important components for understanding and defining the contemporary far right.

Another central issue in the literature is the extent to which these discourses spill over beyond the online environment. Nicholas et al. (2024) show that professionals who work with men who perpetrate domestic violence identify among their participants antifeminist, anti-diversity, and conspiratorial sentiments strongly aligned with manosphere content and right-wing extremism. The authors suggest that this repertoire helps sustain narratives of male victimhood, institutional distrust, and the justification of violence. Thus, the literature indicates that the manosphere is not merely a discursive space of hate, but also an environment of ideological socialization with potential effects on behavior, legitimation of violence, and political dispositions beyond the internet.

In Brazil, this debate directly engages with studies on Bolsonarism and the far right, which show the centrality of gender, sexuality, and family issues in their discursive and political structuring. Avelar (2021) interprets Bolsonarism as a heterogeneous coalition that includes, among other blocs, a “party of the trolls,” marked by permanent antagonism, trolling, and the blurring of truth, rumor, and provocation. Ferreira (2021), in turn, shows how the moral panic surrounding so-called “gender ideology,” the “gay kit,” and sex education was central to the conservative offensive against educational policies and the prevention of gender violence. At the same time, studies on the Brazilian far right’s digital discourse highlight the recurrent use of aggressive, “shameless,” and anti-institutional language, including against the judiciary, as well as digital repertoires of attack against the media, science, health, and democracy (Oliveira et al., 2024; Orso & Massuchin, 2025; Piovezani, 2021).

Finally, the Brazilian literature on backlash and “uncivil society” suggests that the problem is not limited to political rhetoric, but reaches the field of public policy. Segatto et al. (2023) show that the combined action of a radical-right government, conservative groups, and uncivil organizations

contributed to dismantling or hollowing out policies in the fields of gender, sexuality, reproduction, and ethnic-racial relations.

Within this framework, the manosphere deserves attention not only because it constructs an ideology of its own, but also because of its potential to reinforce consensus hostile to gender policies, as can already be seen in recurring attacks on the Maria da Penha Law, sex education, and diversity agendas. It remains underexplored, however, to what extent manosphere groups operate more directly as spaces of political circulation and may come to influence gender policies. This is the gap to which this note seeks to contribute.

3. Methodology

The methodology section of this study is organized into three subsections: 3.1. Data extraction and processing, which describes the process and tools used to collect information from Telegram communities as well as the criteria and methods applied to classify and anonymize the data collected; and 3.2. Data analysis approaches, which details the quantitative and qualitative methods employed to investigate the connections, time series, contents, and discourses in manosphere communities.

3.1. Data Extraction and Processing

This study uses the “Manosphere” database, created in November 2025 (Ricard et al., 2025a). The database began in February 2023 with the publication of the first version of TelegramScrap (Silva, 2023), a free and open-source tool that uses Telegram’s Application Programming Interface (API) through the Telethon library, organizing cycles of data extraction from open groups and channels on the platform. Over the months, the database was expanded and refined through the application of four approaches to identifying conspiracy-theory, political, neo-Nazi, and manosphere communities (we focus on the latter). Although the collection infrastructure is Latin American, this document analyzes exclusively Brazilian communities on Telegram. The groups were identified through keywords, Telegram’s channel recommendation mechanism, and a snowball approach for identifying invitation links using a proprietary algorithm.

The manosphere database contains 85 manosphere communities in Brazil. These communities can be distributed across the following classifications: (i)

Masculinist identities, (ii) Misogyny, (iii) Culture war, (iv) Masculinist self-improvement, and (v) Cryptocurrencies and investments. Together, these communities published 7,029,272 pieces of content between September 2015 and November 2025, totaling a network of 221,254 users. It is important to highlight two considerations regarding this number: first, the total number of users is variable, since members frequently enter and leave communities, meaning that the total recorded represents a temporal snapshot of the data extraction period; second, the same user may belong to several groups, which can generate duplication in the overall count. Although the real number of unique individuals engaged with conspiratorial content may be smaller because of these overlaps, the scale of participation remains significant in the Latin American and Caribbean digital ecosystem. Finally, it is important to note that some communities may fit into more than one category, insofar as their defining characteristic is to assume an identity linked to relational discourses.

It is important to emphasize that the data were extracted exclusively from open communities. These are groups and channels that are not only publicly identifiable but also allow unrestricted access to their content, that is, any Telegram user can join and view the discussions without approval or invitation. In addition, in compliance with regional data protection regulations, particularly Brazil's General Data Protection Law (LGPD - Law No. 13,709/2018), all extracted data were fully anonymized to ensure privacy and compliance with ethical research standards. This anonymization process is not limited to user data, but also includes the identification of communities, ensuring that no group, channel, or participant can be traced through this study. Thus, although the data analyzed come from publicly available content, layers of privacy protection were implemented to prevent any form of direct attribution, reinforcing the ethical commitment to user confidentiality.

3.2. Data analysis

The data analysis combined mixed methods, articulating a quantitative stage and a qualitative stage. The first aimed to measure the presence and temporal evolution of political content in the communities analyzed. The second sought to understand, in depth, how political actors, ideological values, and public policies are discursively constructed in these spaces. This combination made it possible to capture both the prevalence of political content and the meanings and framings attributed to it by community participants.

(i) Quantitative Analysis: We conducted a quantitative analysis of the message base mentioning Jair Bolsonaro and Luiz Inácio Lula da Silva. The choice of these two figures as markers of the communities' political dimension is justified by their centrality in recent Brazilian political polarization, including its affective dimension, marked by strong rejection of the opposing camp and negative identifications between political groups (Fuks & Marques, 2022; Areal, 2022). From this sub-dataset, we examined the frequency of mentions of the two politicians and their variation over time through time series analysis, with the aim of identifying peaks, cycles, and moments of intensification in political conversation. This stage allowed us to assess the extent to which politics appears recurrently in these communities, rather than only episodically or reactively to isolated events. It should be noted that this choice does not exhaust the political dimension of the communities analyzed, since other actors, such as Nikolas Ferreira, and other terms, such as "feminism" or "Maria da Penha," also appear frequently in the corpus and are examined in the qualitative stage. The choice of Bolsonaro and Lula as quantitative markers is justified by their ability to offer a robust, comparable, and longitudinally stable proxy for assessing the recurrence of politicization across ten years of data.

(ii) Qualitative Analysis: We carried out a Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) (Fairclough, 2005), centered on content selected for its analytical relevance. Unlike an exhaustive reading of the entire corpus, this stage focused on exemplary messages and images in order to understand how political discourses are articulated with the construction of masculinities, femininities, social enemies, and moral threats. The selection of content did not seek statistical representativeness, but rather interpretive relevance, privileging examples that condensed recurring discursive patterns, particularly around support for or rejection of political figures and attacks on gender policies. In practice, selection was conducted through iterative readings of the corpus by more than one researcher, focusing on messages that illustrated patterns identified as recurrent across different communities and categories. Divergent or ambiguous cases were discussed jointly in order to reduce individual interpretive bias. Even so, we recognize that any qualitative selection involves analytical judgments that cannot be entirely neutralized, which reinforces the importance of complementary readings and future research with systematic sampling protocols.

4. Results

4.1. The *Manosphere* is Political

Based on the literature on affective polarization (Areal, 2022), we start from the understanding that recent Brazilian politics has been strongly polarized around two figures: Jair Bolsonaro, associated with the far-right camp, and Luiz Inácio Lula da Silva, associated with the progressive camp. In this sense, we conducted a quantitative survey of mentions of both politicians in the Telegram database.

We observed similar volumes of mentions of Bolsonaro (8,418) and Lula (7,558) over the last ten years, indicating that political discussion consistently cuts across these communities. Mentions become relevant from 2019 onward and grow more sharply beginning in 2021. In Bolsonaro's case, there is a peak in August and September 2021. The greatest combined volume of mentions of both occurs between December 2022 and January 2023, in the period following the presidential election. This suggests that the politicization of the *manosphere* is not episodic, but follows central moments in the national conjuncture. Also noteworthy is the reversal observed from 2023 onward: mentions of Lula surpass those of Bolsonaro and remain higher in 2024 and 2025. This suggests that after Bolsonaro's electoral defeat, the *manosphere* did not demobilize; it redirected its focus toward the adversary in power. Hostility toward the progressive camp appears, in these spaces, to be more mobilizing than support for the camp with which these groups have greater ideological affinity. In other words, hatred of the enemy may function as a more effective driver of engagement than identification with a leader. This has implications for thinking about the *manosphere* in 2026: it tends to operate more intensely as a vector of opposition than as a support base.

Table 1. Mentions of “Bolsonaro” and “Lula” in *Manosphere* Communities (2016-2025)

	Bolsonaro	Lula	Total
2016	1	0	1
2017	0	0	0
2018	0	0	0
2019	932	247	1179

2020	573	48	621
2021	1691	502	2193
2022	1864	1419	3283
2023	1410	2424	3834
2024	1118	1829	2947
2025	829	1089	1918
TOTAL	8418	7558	15976

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Graphic 1. Mentions of “Bolsonaro” and “Lula” in Manosphere Communities (2016-2025)

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Quantitative analysis alone does not allow us to infer the stand of these mentions. For this reason, we conducted a qualitative reading of selected content, seeking to identify whether it expressed anti-Lula, pro-Bolsonaro, anti-Bolsonaro, pro-Lula, broader anti-politics positions, or whether it did not permit clear classification. Given the high degree of irony, ambiguity, and implicit references present in this universe, we understand that automated classifications, such as sentiment analysis, would be insufficient to adequately capture the meanings produced in these interactions. The qualitative analysis that follows indicates that there is no single or homogeneous partisan affiliation, but it does reveal elements of discourses close to the far right.

To understand how this politicization operates, and above all not only how much it appears, the qualitative analysis examined the discursive repertoires structuring the worldview in these groups. More than mapping partisan affinities, the aim is to identify the patterns of meaning that organize the

relationship between masculinity, authority, moral enemies, and public policy. The five repertoires below condense the most recurrent and analytically relevant elements in the corpus.

4.2. Core Elements of Manosphere Ideology

We examined the main repertoires mobilized in manosphere groups. More than seeking a homogeneous political identity, we are interested in understanding how these spaces construct a worldview of their own, marked by the defense of gender hierarchies, the production of moral and political enemies, the symbolic legitimation of violence, and hostility to equality agendas. In several of these respects, we observe convergences with repertoires already identified in the literature on the Brazilian far right.

Gender Hierarchies and the Ideal of Dominant Masculinity

Brazilian literature points to the centrality of cis-heteronormative, anti-gender, and anti-LGBTQIA+ discourses in the construction of certain political repertoires (Assis & Silva, 2024). These studies show that the reaffirmation of traditional gender roles, the pathologization of dissident sexualities (Alixandrino et al., 2026), and the association between masculinity, authority, and social order are recurrent traits of the far right (Amato & Fuchs, 2022; Miguel, 2021).

In the selected qualitative material, messages supporting Bolsonaro and the broader Bolsonarist camp are frequently observed through different enunciations. Certain discourses associate Bolsonaro with positive values within the masculinist universe, which is articulated to the idea of authority, respect, and the restoration of a masculine order perceived as lost. In one message, for example, a user states that Bolsonaro was elected because he represented “a figure of respect and authority”. Support for Bolsonaro appears as a sign that “men are waking up”, that is, as evidence that he embodies the masculinity values exalted by this redpill community, in which the very “red pill” refers precisely to the idea of awakening. In this repertoire, support for Bolsonaro is read less in programmatic terms than as identification with an ideal of strong, hierarchical, and disciplinarian masculinity.

Since you brought up the military era, I have my theories that Bolsonaro was elected because he shows a figure of respect and authority. That is something many young men long for today, especially those raised by single mothers... This is a sign that young men are waking up... another good sign is Jordan Peterson's fame as the "father they never had" all over the world. The guy is famous even in Russia.

Community in the category "Masculinist Identity", December/2020

In other words, there is an association between political leadership and hypermasculinity. Bolsonaro, in particular, is frequently portrayed as the embodiment of an excessive, sexualized, and dominant masculinity. In one message, a user lists, in hyperbolic fashion, signs of virility attributed to the former president, such as marriages, children, testosterone, and sexual performance, concluding that Lula "does not have that power." The content is evidently fantastical, but its analytical value lies precisely in what it celebrates: sexual potency, physical strength, and reproductive capacity as desirable attributes of masculine leadership.

Bolsonaro has the superpower of being improbable. He has been married to 3 women. 5 children. Testosterone 2120 on a recent test. Penis 50 cm erect on a recent test. He supports all Brazilian soccer teams. Athlete's physique. Does Lula have that power? No, right?

Community in the category "Masculinist Identity", December/2024

By contrast, attacks against men, such as Lula, leverage alleged lack of sexual capacity:

Janja bought a sofa and a bed costing more than 50K each; I don't know why such an expensive bed if that drunk bastard can't even fuck her. Lula didn't get vaccinated because if he had, he would have died trying to get his own dick hard

Community in the category "Misogyny," April/2023

At the same time, the same logic that values traditional masculine performance also ridicules means deemed artificial for attaining it. An anti-Bolsonaro meme, for example, mocks a supposed adherence to the “aesthetics pill”, suggesting that appearance-oriented procedures would make his masculinity less authentic. This reveals an important tension: these groups value male optimization, but ridicule signs of excessive vanity or artificiality.

BOLSOMITO(LIXO) TOMOU A ESTÉTICA PILL

BOLSOMYTH(TRASH) TOOK THE ESTHETIC PILL

Community in the category “Masculinist identity”

Another recurring element is the use of vocabulary typical of the manosphere to qualify political actors. Expressions such as “Lula is an incel”, references to the “blackpill” and the “honk pill,” show how the grammar of these forums is transferred to the interpretation of national politics. This is not merely a style of language, but a lens for reading the world in which success, failure, morality, domination, and masculine resentment also come to organize the perception of public figures. This reading is articulated with a valorization of cynical, transgressive, and anti-institutional attitudes. In one message, Bolsonaro is defined as “the biggest Honk Pill in history”, referring to a posture of mockery, chaos, and contempt for norms. In this framework, the admirable politician is not the most responsible or coherent one, but the one who confronts limits, challenges institutions, and turns provocation into a mark of authenticity.

I think Bolsonaro is the biggest Honk Pill in history, it's like he kicked over the whole setup and said fuck it [\[link\]](#)

Community in the category "Masculinist Identity", December/2020

In other cases, this repertoire is mobilized in a more ambiguous and pedagogical way, as a kind of moral lesson directed at community members themselves. In one message, for example, Lula is read through the grammar of the blackpill as someone who, in theory, ought to occupy a subordinate position because he is described as a “manlet,” “ugly,” “illiterate,” and “fat.” Yet the author recognizes that he “got what he wanted in life,” even while reinterpreting this success in depreciatory terms by portraying him as corrupt and subordinate to greater interests. The message thus shifts the blackpill from absolute fatalism toward an ethics of masculine action. It shows how categories typical of the manosphere are appropriated not only to classify politicians, but also to produce models of conduct, resilience, and self-understanding among participants themselves.

In blackpill logic, Lula should still be a loser: manlet, ugly, illiterate, fat... Anyway, he got what he wanted in life, even if in the end he is a lackey for bigger people, he got what he wanted. But he did a lot of shit, stole and so on, and you are not willing to do that? Then do not lament, be proud of your morals and stand tall. But remaining inert should not be an option.

Community in the category "Masculinist Identity", December/2025

The notion of power also appears heavily sexualized. In part of the content, being a dominant man is equivalent to exercising power over political adversaries and over women. The language mobilized to talk about political dispute is often one of sexual humiliation of the enemy (“Bolsonaro is going to cum condensed milk in the left’s ass. He already has my vote, 2022, he’s elected”, January/2021). In other cases, masculine power is explicitly associated with control over women close to leaders, as if the ability to dominate a partner were evidence of strength and authority. This logic reinforces the idea that legitimate masculinity is inseparable from command, possession, and the subordination of others.

Maybe Lula has more control over that ugly Janja than Bolsonaro has over Michelle.

Community in the category “Masculinist identity”, August/2023

This pattern becomes even more evident when we observe how women in politics are treated. Hostility toward women goes beyond partisan polarization and reaches the very legitimacy of their presence in the public sphere, as illustrated by the exchange below, in which the user declares that he would rather vote “for Stalin” than for any woman.

Selected messages, translated from Portuguese:

“I would never vote for a woman. It could be Stalin versus a right-wing woman. I’d vote for Stalin.”

“Imagine the apocalyptic scenario: Janja versus Michelle Bolsonaro.”

“That’s misogynist.”

“Yes.”

“There are men better than that pain in the ass from Janja.”

“Crazy woman.”

Community in the category “Masculinist Identities”, May/2025

We found content that attacks and ridicules women that have lots of visibility, such as first-lady Janja and prior first-lady Michelle Bolsonaro,

through sexual insults, public humiliation, and insinuations about intimate behavior. In one of the messages, for example, the possibility that Michelle Bolsonaro could become “the first female president with an OnlyFans” is mocked. This is typical of the redpill repertoire: disqualifying women through their sexualization, reducing their public presence to moral judgments about the body and sexuality.

I HAS TO BE DICTATOR-SHIP LIKE XI JINPING'S, BABY

Community in the category "Misogyny", August/2024

The attacks directed at Janja and Michelle Bolsonaro are consistent with findings by Ricard et al. (2025b), which identify political visibility as a central factor in the intensification of technology-facilitated gender-based violence against women in politics. Women with national prominence become preferred targets of campaigns of hostility, humiliation, and delegitimation aimed not only at their political positions, but at their very presence in the public sphere.

In Michelle Bolsonaro's case, the content analyzed also suggests an important dynamic identified in the literature: women situated on the right can likewise suffer attacks from allies when they are perceived as transgressing expectations of ideological purity, femininity, or loyalty, which highlights the disciplinary character of gender-based political violence.

And that whore Michele Bolsonaro, taking a picture with a tranny who ran for office under the PL, a “right-wing trans woman,” Michele also takes it up the ass for a gay and wanted to pass 100 feminist laws under the PT bitch government. Michele used to be known as “the chamber’s lunchbox”; she is also a single mother. This is the right against the “degenerate left.” Only here will you see these frauds exposed. Symptoms: conservative liberals.

Community in the category “Misogyny”, August/2024

Dehumanization, Exclusion, and the Legitimation of Violence

In some cases, the misogynistic discourse observed in the communities goes beyond symbolic humiliation and slides into more explicit forms of dehumanization. Here, women and political adversaries cease to be treated as legitimate subjects of rights and come to be presented as inferior beings, disposable, or subject to violent correction. This dimension matters because, as the literature on dehumanization argues, denying the full humanity of certain groups helps naturalize their exclusion and make fantasies or practices of aggression against them more acceptable (Haslam, 2006; Kteily & Bruneau, 2017). In the Brazilian context, this is articulated with a political environment in which sexism, violent language, and hostility against women in politics have already been identified as mechanisms for maintaining gender hierarchies (Caldas-Coulthard, 2022; Kulaitis, 2024).

She is a leftist, a commie, and a woman in politics, so you can hit her. LOOK AT THE PUNCH ON THE DRUNK TURTLE.

Community in the category “Misogyny”, April/2023

In the content analyzed, this logic appears when aggression against women in politics is trivialized or celebrated, to the point, for example, of advocating the abandonment of or abortion of daughters. Although these messages often circulate in a joking or ironic tone, they should not be reduced to mere “dark humor”. On the contrary, they participate in the production of an imaginary in which violence against women is relativized and control over their bodies appears as a masculine prerogative. This type of enunciation is consistent with what the literature on gender-based political violence

describes as symbolic and discursive strategies aimed at restricting women's presence and legitimacy in the public sphere (Kulaitis, 2024).

If the child is a girl there are two options: abortion or cigarettes.

Community in the category "Masculinist Identity", December/2024

Finally, the political content analyzed reinforces a finding already identified in a previous study on the Brazilian manosphere (Ricard et al., 2025a): hatred against women rarely appears in isolation, and is often accompanied by racism, classism, and, in other moments of the corpus, LGBTphobia. What we observe in political discourses confirms this imbrication. In attacks on Lula, for example, explicitly classist and racist formulations appear, associating his electorate with "Northeasterners", "favela dwellers", and the poor as inferior, undesirable, or threatening categories.

I hate what Lula represents. Northeasterners and favela dwellers identify with him; therefore, since I am neither Northeastern nor a favela dweller, I have the right to want a president who represents me. Lula does not address my class in his speeches and does not make policies that benefit me. I am elitist and I prefer a scenario in which it is easier to exploit the poor, subordinates, etc.

Community in the category "Masculinist identity", January/2025

In extreme messages, we even found advocacy of extermination measures or reproductive control aimed at racialized and regionalized groups, such as compulsory abortion for Black people or reproductive restrictions for Northeastern families. These examples show that, in these spaces, the politicization of misogyny is articulated with other forms of dehumanization, reinforcing a hierarchical, exclusionary, and violent worldview. The literature on recent Brazilian political discourse helps support this reading by showing that Bolsonaroism and the far right in the country have been traversed by racism, xenophobia, sexism, and violent language against women and minorities (Caldas-Coulthard, 2022).

THE ABORTION BILL EVERY HUMAN BEING TRULY WANTS

- > mandatory abortion for all Black people
- > if the pregnancy results from miscegenation, abortion and 12 years in prison for the mother (if the mother is Black, abortion, sterilization, and 12 years in prison)
- > a maximum of 1 child per Northeastern family (if they have more, abortion and cancellation of Bolsa Família)
- > São Paulo families are required to train and teach proper Portuguese to their offspring
- > every father has the constitutional right to choose whether he wants an abortion if the fetus is a girl or disabled (the mother has no legal right to choose)

Community in the category "Masculinist Identity", October/2024

Moral and Anti-gender Agenda

In Brazil, the defense of a moral agenda appears in the literature as a structuring element of the far right and Bolsonarism, articulating religion, the traditional family, antifeminism, and opposition to so-called "gender ideology" (Miguel, 2021). In this repertoire, gender and sexuality cease to be sectoral issues and begin to function as central markers distinguishing order from decadence, the people from the enemy (Marques & Carlos, 2025). We found posts that valorize "conservative" identities, articulating opposition to abortion, feminism, drugs, so-called "gender ideology", and the left in general. In these cases, politics, sexual morality, and masculine identity appear strongly intertwined.

→ Every nationalist, patriot, conservative must say NO to abortion, feminism, drugs, gender ideology, the victimization of criminals, civilian disarmament, censorship of social networks, etc. All people who still intend to preserve moral values must say NO to Lula and the PT. 🇧🇷🇧🇷

Community in the category "Masculinist identity", October/2022

This promotion of a moral agenda goes beyond the partisan question, since it can also be found in messages that attack Bolsonaro and his allies:

Are 3-year-old children being trafficked for sexual objects, torture, and death? Who is distancing the authority of the FATHER from the child? From the baby? Feminism. Both the damned Bolsonaro and the damned Damaris bitch Alves turned Brazil into a stronghold of feminism. Bolsonaro is a Jew lackey. Therefore he is AN ENEMY OF HUMANITY!

Community in the category "Masculinist Identity", August/2025

Anti-leftism and the Culture War

In Brazil, the literature shows that the far right frequently frames issues of gender, diversity, and rights as part of a broader threat associated with communism, cultural Marxism, or the destruction of the nation. This conspiratorial framing transforms political adversaries into civilizational enemies and helps connect sexual morality, anti-PT (Worker's Party) sentiment, and culture war (Avelar, 2021; Miguel, 2021).

Attacks against Lula, for example, appear recurrently and tend to mobilize accusations of corruption, incompetence, moral weakness, and association with communism. Rather than being limited to conventional political criticism, these messages frequently construct Lula as a symbol of national degradation, inverting the opposition between a supposedly virile, orderly, and patriotic pole on the one hand, and a corrupt, decadent, and threatening pole on the other.

In fact Lula is not lost in government... everything they do is consistent with the communist agenda of breaking the country.

Community in the category "Masculinist Identity", February/2025

Beyond anti-Lula sentiment, the content also reveals the presence of a broader anti-left discourse, in which "the left" appears as a totalizing category disqualified as a whole. In the examples analyzed, left-wing people are portrayed as "stupid", "ignorant", and easily manipulated, while symbols, agendas, and milestones historically associated with the progressive field are resignified as expressions of ideological threat. In some cases, this framing takes on more extreme contours, bringing the left closer to

authoritarian communism, fascism, or even Nazism through simplifactory and historically distorted analogies. Attempts also appear to delegitimize agendas associated with the left, such as International Women’s Rights Day (March 8), presented in one message as a “communist” creation. Taken together, this content suggests that, in these groups, the left is not merely the target of political opposition, but is constructed as a radical other, morally corrupted and incompatible with the values exalted by the community.

International Women’s Day is a date created by murderous communists! And it is the left itself that says so!

Community in the category “Masculinist Self-improvement”, March/2025

Anti-institutionalism and Rejection of Traditional Politics

Another recurring trait identified in the literature is anti-institutionalism, which combines denunciation of corruption, rejection of traditional politics, and disqualification of democratic mediations. In far-right populism, this repertoire allows leadership to be constructed as a legitimate outsider while attacking the political system, the press, and institutions of oversight (Avelar, 2021; Marques & Carlos, 2025; Oliveira et al., 2024).

The discursive set analyzed combines rejection of both Lula and Bolsonaro, sliding into a broader critique of institutional politics. In this repertoire, both appear as representatives of the same corrupt system, rather than as truly antagonistic poles. Messages such as “Bolsonaro is weak and the PT is the devil” or “Lula and Bozo are two sides of the same rotten and corrupt coin” illustrate this logic well.

In part of the sample, this rejection is articulated with a more general disillusionment with representative politics. Rather than expressing partisan identification, some users say that “no politician represents me” and extend their rejection to figures from different ideological camps.

I am not a fan of politicians; none of them represent me. There is no way to support a politician who is extremely cynical, breaks thousands of campaign

promises, and mocks the people. I want Bolsonaro, Lula, Ciro Gomes, Marina Silva, Aécio Neves, etc. to go fuck themselves.

Community in the category "Masculinist Identity", November/2024

We found a community whose very description (bio) already ties misogyny/sexual morality to political and religious identity, making belonging boundaries explicit ("who can be here"). A channel bio combines (i) moralizing rejection of women ("promiscuous behavior"), (ii) Christian identity ("We are Christians"), and (iii) politics - but not clearly associated with one of the camps, since it rejects representatives of both: "No PT supporter can thrive here. Miserable PT supporters, MBL is worse than PT. PT is trash!" In these cases, politics is less a space of programmatic dispute and more an identity and moral marker used to distinguish allies from enemies.

“

We do not hate women, we simply do not agree with the promiscuous behavior of most of them. We are Christians, respect our faith!

No PT supporter can thrive here.

Get out of this group, you damned one!

Miserable PT supporters, MBL is worse than PT.

PT is trash!

Bio of a community in the category "Masculinist identity"

One cross-cutting finding deserves emphasis: the manosphere is not monolithically Bolsonarist. In several groups, Bolsonaro is attacked in the very terms of masculinist grammar: described as "weak", "hypocritical", or "incoherent" with the values his supporters claim. This does not weaken the argument about ideological convergence between the manosphere and the far right, but it qualifies it in an important way. What unites these groups is not loyalty to a specific leader or party, but adherence to a set of values (gender hierarchy, moral order, hostility to feminism and the left) that no politician fully satisfies. This internal heterogeneity has an important practical consequence: it makes the manosphere more resilient and adaptable than a movement of support for a specific figure. Its repertoires can be mobilized by different candidates and agendas, as long as they activate the same moral and identity triggers.

4.3. Attacks against Gender Policies in Manosphere Communities

The results indicate that the politicization of the manosphere also appears in the way public policies related to gender, violence against women, sexuality, and reproduction are framed in these groups. These policies are often presented as threats to men, the family, and the moral order. What emerges from the content, therefore, is not only specific disagreement regarding certain measures, but a broader hostility to the very legitimacy of gender policies.

Attacks Against the Legislation Protecting Women

Previous studies show that the Maria da Penha Law has been a recurrent target of attacks in conspiratorial communities (Alves et al., 2025a). We observed a similar dynamic in manosphere groups. In these spaces, the law is less understood as a public policy to protect against domestic violence and more converted into a symbol of supposed female supremacy and of a legal system organized against men. Rather than criticism of specific aspects of its implementation prevailing, what is more frequently observed is a broader framing according to which the state has supposedly been captured by feminism and now operates through instruments of male persecution.

LAWS LIKE THE MARIA DA PENHA LAW ARE SEXIST AND INFAMOUS, LIKE ALL THE OTHERS THAT PRIVILEGE WOMEN TO THE DETRIMENT OF MEN, CHILDREN, AND BABIES.

Community in the category "Masculinist Identity", August/2021

In the content analyzed, the Maria da Penha Law appears above all as an object of legal and affective resentment. It is described as a mechanism of "false accusation", revenge, extortion, or arbitrary removal of rights by women, especially former partners. In several messages, the law is associated with fear of being removed from the home, loss of property, protective measures deemed unjust, and female advantage in conjugal disputes. This framing not only distorts the meaning of the law, but reinscribes it as one of the main risks of heterosexual relationships, strongly converging with MGTOW, blackpill, and other currents that discourage affective ties with women.

This pattern is particularly visible in messages advising men to avoid marriage, cohabitation, or any kind of long-term commitment, on the grounds that women could mobilize the Maria da Penha Law and other norms to obtain money, housing, or power over their partner. In such cases, legislation protecting women ceases to appear as an institutional response to gender violence and comes to be treated as proof that men are “second-class citizens” or preferred targets of the system. The law thus functions less as law and more as a condensed symbol of perceived misandry, fear of attachment, and antifeminist hostility.

There's cattle who talk about marrying under total separation of property. It seems they have never heard of false accusations under the Maria da Penha Law and feminism. My friend, stealing a man's property under these absurd laws we have is the easiest thing there is. You want to let a woman live in your house?! Try it and then tell me. If you want to shack up, do it only in a rented home...

⚠️ In our live with Caio yesterday, two viewers had been removed from their homes through protective measures based on false accusations. Watch the full live 🗨️

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mtnAaFORHzE>

Community in the category "Masculinist Identity", July/2021

We also observed the circulation of disinformative content about the very origin of the law, with the aim of discrediting its historical and symbolic basis. Some messages do not limit themselves to contesting the application of the law, but attack Maria da Penha's own story, suggesting that the legislation was born from a lie or a false accusation. This movement matters because it shifts the discussion from the sphere of implementation to that of the legal framework's very legitimacy, opening space for calls for repeal, revision, or weakening. There are also attacks on other laws protecting women, assembled into lists that present different norms as part of a supposed anti-male system. In these materials, laws on psychological violence, sexual harassment, protective measures, prenatal child support, or protection in public spaces are reinterpreted as a coherent block of female privileges and unfair punishments for men.

And this is only a small part of the total number of anti-male laws; being a man in Brazil is the status of a second-class citizen, and getting married makes you third-class.

Community in the category "Masculinist identity", May/2025

From the standpoint of public policy, this type of discourse matters because it contributes to corroding the social legitimacy of central instruments for protecting women. Although the material analyzed does not allow us to automatically assert direct impact on legislative decisions or state implementation, it shows the production and circulation of consensuses hostile to gender legislation, capable of reinforcing pressures for normative revision, disinformation about rights, and resistance to the application of protective measures. In other words, the problem is not merely discursive: it is the construction of a symbolic environment adverse to the sustainability of public policies aimed at preventing and confronting violence against women.

THE PENHA LIE MUST BE REPEALED.

Community in the category "Cryptocurrencies and investments", October/2025

Sex Education

Sex education also appears recurrently in the corpus as a target of attacks and moral panic. The predominant framing does not present it as a tool for information, violence prevention, health promotion, or child protection, but as a mechanism of early sexualization, invasion of children's space, and preparation for abuse. In several messages, content related to sex education is described in alarmist terms, as if it exposed children to sexual practices, "indoctrination", or moral contamination. In this key, sex education is converted into a threat rather than a policy of care.

These same children are also being instructed to pretend they are being raped or sodomized as part of their “sex education”.

Community in the category “Culture war”, June/2022

This framing rarely appears in isolation. In many messages, sex education, “gender ideology,” feminism, abortion, and LGBT rights appear fused into the same semantic chain, as if they were part of a single project to destroy the family, morality, and parental authority. This fusion is typical of culture-war repertoires: different themes are articulated in emotional and simplified ways to produce a common enemy and mobilize rejection. In this way, sex education ceases to be debated in its concrete objectives and instead functions as an ideological marker of a supposed progressive offensive against children and families.

APPARENTLY, THEY ARE INCREASINGLY TIRED OF STATE INTERVENTION IN CHILDHOOD EDUCATION AND, ABOVE ALL, OF THE INDOCTRINATION OF GENDER IDEOLOGY AND LGBTI+ MOVEMENTS

Community in the category “Culture war”, March/2022

This framing is relevant for the analysis of public policy because it helps delegitimize educational initiatives aimed at preventing violence, promoting sexual and reproductive health, and confronting abuse. By turning sex education into a synonym for perversion, indoctrination, or threat to childhood, these discourses produce an environment of suspicion that makes it harder to formulate, implement, and publicly defend rights-based educational policies. Once again, it is not merely a matter of moral disagreement, but of a dispute over the legitimacy of public policies aimed at the protection and autonomy of children, adolescents, and women.

Abortion

In the abortion subcorpus, the term appears less as the object of debate on public policy and more as a moral signifier that concentrates multiple anxieties of the masculinist ecosystem. Abortion is framed as murder, infanticide, or a “death agenda”, but also as proof of the supposed perversity of women, feminism, and the left. In this material, it operates as a point of condensation among misogyny, antifeminism, moral conservatism, religion,

anti-leftism, conspiratorial imaginaries, and dehumanization of the adversary.

Abortion is a human sacrifice, not health care.

Community in the category "Culture war", September/2024

One of the most striking aspects is that abortion does not appear only as a specific issue, but as a node articulating a broader worldview. When these groups talk about abortion, they are also talking about who should hold power, what place women should occupy, what counts as a legitimate family, and who should be treated as an enemy of the social order. The subject in favor of abortion, for example, is often demonized as an "abortionist", a category that designates not merely a political position, but a degraded moral type associated with civilizational decadence, corruption of customs, and destruction of life.

"When you see a soul announcing abortion as something benign, you will know that the prince of darkness reigns there, and that its eternity is for now written in the book of death."

- Padre Pio of Pietrelcina

Community in the category "Cryptocurrencies and investments", August/2025

This process has important implications for the field of public policy. Once displaced from the terrain of rights, public health, and reproductive justice to that of absolute moral condemnation, abortion comes to function as an ideological shortcut for mobilizing rejection of different gender and diversity agendas. As a result, not only is a qualified public debate on reproductive rights rendered unviable, but a broader repertoire of hostility toward policies aimed at bodily autonomy, sexual health, and recognition of gender inequalities is also strengthened. In this sense, the material suggests that abortion occupies a strategic role in the manosphere as a point of convergence between misogyny and politics, helping organize moral and ideological boundaries that go beyond the reproductive issue itself.

5. Discussion

The results of this technical note reinforce the hypothesis that the Brazilian manosphere on Telegram should be understood as an ecosystem of ideological socialization, and not merely as a set of communities focused on affective frustrations or advice on masculinity. The quantitative analysis shows that politics appears recurrently over time, accompanying decisive moments in the national conjuncture. The qualitative analysis, in turn, indicates that this politicization is organized around moral, affective, and discursive repertoires of its own, marked by gender hierarchies, male victimhood, dehumanization, and hostility to rights. In several respects, these repertoires converge with elements associated in the literature with the Brazilian far right, although without producing uniform partisan affiliation among all groups and participants.

In this sense, the data confirm the central hypothesis, but with an important qualification: the politicization of the manosphere is more ideological than partisan. It is not organized around fixed loyalties to leaders or parties, but around a repertoire of values (hierarchy, order, hostility to feminism and the left) that can be activated by different political actors. This makes its influence potentially broader and more durable than that of a movement supporting a specific figure.

Rather than being one topic among others, misogyny operates in these spaces as a political grammar. It organizes perceptions about authority, social decadence, public enemies, merit, order, and legitimate violence. In this sense, attacks on women, feminists, LGBTQIA+ people, and subordinated groups do not appear as marginal deviations, but as part of a worldview that naturalizes hierarchies and turns inequality into a normative principle. This finding converges with the international literature, which identifies overlaps among the manosphere, the far right, and conservative movements such as tradwives, in which antifeminism and the valorization of traditional gender roles reinforce the centrality of misogyny in radicalization processes (Stotzer & Nelson, 2025).

This ideological structure has a characteristic that makes it particularly difficult to combat: it operates in a metastatic rather than centralized way. Just as metastases do not depend on an original tumor to keep growing, manosphere repertoires reproduce, specialize, and adapt without depending on formal coordination or a single leadership. Communities differentiate internally (masculinist self-help, moral antifeminism, culture

war, anti-institutionalism), yet maintain a common core of values. This means that dismantling one group, banning one influencer, or defeating one specific candidate does not dissolve the ecosystem: it reorganizes, mutates, and reappears in another morphology. Any intervention strategy needs to take this into account.

From the standpoint of public policy, the findings are especially relevant. Hostility toward the Maria da Penha Law, sex education, and reproductive rights suggests that the manosphere acts not only in the sphere of opinion, but also in the symbolic erosion of the legitimacy of policies aimed at protection, prevention, and gender equality. Although the corpus does not allow us to automatically infer direct effects on legislative changes or government decisions, it does show the circulation of hostile consensuses that may reinforce regressive pressures, disinformation about rights, and social resistance to the implementation of these policies.

This study has limitations. We worked with open Telegram communities and, in the qualitative stage, with content selected for analytical relevance rather than statistical representativeness. This selection criterion entails a “risk of bias”: the examples chosen tend to be the most expressive or condensational of patterns, which may overestimate the corpus’s radicality. Future research can deepen the analysis of forwarding networks, circulation between masculinist communities and explicitly political groups, and the effects of these repertoires on electoral campaigns, anti-rights mobilizations, and episodes of offline violence - an especially pertinent issue in light of the 2026 electoral cycle.

References

Amato, B., & Fuchs, J. J. B. (2022). Discursos de ódio de gênero e subjetivação: articulações entre masculinismo e extrema-direita. In F. A. de Almeida (Org.), *Violência e gênero: análises, perspectivas e desafios* (pp. 77-92). Editora Científica Digital. <https://doi.org/10.37885/220709519>

Alixandrino, J. A., Rodrigues, M. A., & Souza, L. S. de. (2026). Democracia e gênero: O avanço dos discursos da extrema-direita e os ataques do bolsonarismo aos corpos LGBTQIAPN+. *COR LGBTQIA+*, 1(10), 84-98. <https://doi.org/10.56579/cor.v1i10.2489>

Alves, M. A., Ricard, J. C., Silva, E. C. de M., Celestino, G. N. B., Rocha, G., & Vitória, S. (2025a). Nota técnica 003.2025: Desordem informacional sobre violência de gênero e ataques contra a Lei Maria da Penha no Telegram (07 de agosto de 2025). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18011990>

Alves, M. A., Ricard, J. C., Silva, E. C. de M., Celestino, G. N. B., Rocha, G., & Vitória, S. (2025b). Nota técnica 004.2025: Desordem informacional sobre educação sexual como vetor de mobilização política conservadora no Telegram. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17208688>

Areal, J. (2022). “Them” without “us”: Negative identities and affective polarization in Brazil. *Political Research Exchange*, 4(1), 2117635. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2474736X.2022.2117635>

Assis, L. S. de, & Silva, D. da C. P. (2024). Discursos coloniais sobre gênero e sexualidade em enunciados da extrema-direita brasileira. *Diálogo das Letras*, 13, e02415. <https://doi.org/10.22297/2316-17952024v13e02415>

Avelar, I. (2021). Genealogia discursiva do bolsonarismo. *Aisthesis*, 70, 169-198. <https://doi.org/10.7764/aisth.70.8>

Caldas-Coulthard, C. R. (2022). Sexismo cotidiano banal e persistente na política brasileira. *Ilha do Desterro*, 75(3), 55-73. <https://doi.org/10.5007/2175-8026.2022.e86409>

Fairclough, N. (2005). Peripheral vision: Discourse analysis in organization studies: The case for critical realism. *Organization Studies*, 26(6), 915-939. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0170840605054610>

Ferreira, G. L. G. P. (2021). ‘Once you say the word gender, people become afraid’: The consequences of the gender backlash in education in Brasil. *International Journal for Crime, Justice and Social Democracy*, 10(4), 223-238. <https://doi.org/10.5204/ijcjsd.2074>

Fuks, M., & Marques, P. H. (2022). Polarização e contexto: medindo e explicando a polarização política no Brasil. *Opinião Pública*, 28, 560-593. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1807-01912022283560>

Ging, D. (2019). Alphas, betas, and incels: Theorizing the masculinities of the manosphere. *Men and Masculinities*, 22(4), 638–657. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1097184X17706401>

Gottzén, L., & Areschoug, S. (2025). Young masculinities and political subjectivity in and beyond the manosphere. *Young: Nordic Journal of Youth Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/11033088251371897>

Haslam, N. (2006). Dehumanization: An integrative review. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, 10(3), 252-264. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327957pspr1003_4

Kteily, N. S., & Bruneau, E. (2017). Backlash: The politics and real-world consequences of minority group dehumanization. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 43(1), 87-104. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0146167216675334>

Kulaitis, L. F. M. (2024). “Os homens estruturam um mundo deles e para eles”: A violência política de gênero como estratégia ortodoxa de reprodução do campo político. *Mediações - Revista de Ciências Sociais*, 29(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.5433/2176-6665.2024v29n1e49152>

Mamié, R., Horta Ribeiro, M., & West, R. (2021). Are anti-feminist communities gateways to the far right? Evidence from Reddit and YouTube. In *Proceedings of the 13th ACM Web Science Conference 2021 (WebSci '21)* (pp. 139–147). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3447535.3462504>

Marques, M. de S., & Carlos, E. (2025). O populismo de extrema-direita no governo Bolsonaro: uma abordagem discursiva. *Sociologias*, 27, e140107. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1807-0337/e140107>

Miguel, L. F. (2021). O mito da “ideologia de gênero” no discurso da extrema-direita brasileira. *Cadernos Pagu*, 62, e216216. <https://doi.org/10.1590/18094449202100620016>

Nicholas, L., Clark, S., Agius, C., & Cook, K. (2024). Antifeminist, manosphere and right-wing extremist sentiment among men who use domestic and family violence: Masculinism, misinformation, and the justificatory logics of violence. *NORMA: Nordic Journal for Masculinity Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/18902138.2024.2430513>

Oliveira, A. L. A. M., Drinóczi, T., & Miranda, M. V. (2024). Far-right discourse in Brazil: Shameless language as a common practice? *Journal of Language and Politics*, 24(5), 760-782. <https://doi.org/10.1075/jlp.23120.oli>

Orso, M., & Goulart Massuchin, M. (2025). A extrema-direita digital no Brasil: grupos ativistas e repertório discursivo. *Revista Uruguaya de Ciencia Política*, 34, 1-32. <https://doi.org/10.26851/RUCP.34.10>

Piovezani, C. (2021). Discursos da extrema-direita no Brasil: Uma análise de pronunciamentos de Jair Bolsonaro. *Revista Latinoamericana de Estudios del Discurso*, 21(2), 85-100. <https://doi.org/10.35956/v.21.n2.2021.p.85-100>

Preston, K., Halpin, M., & Lockyer, D. (2025). Incels and gender inequality: changing tides in defining the far right. *Social Problems*, spaf052. <https://doi.org/10.1093/socpro/spaf052>

Ricard, J. C., Cugler, E., Alves, M. A., Celestino, G., Rocha, G., & Vitória, S. (2025a). Redes de ódio e violência contra mulheres: mapeamento da machosfera brasileira no Telegram e modelos de monetização. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17706952>

Ricard, J., Spinardi, A., Quitério de Gois, A., & Cugler, E. (2025b). Technology-facilitated gender-based violence against women in politics in Brazil. ALIGN / Data-Pop Alliance. <https://www.alignplatform.org/resources/technology-facilitated-gender-based-violence-against-women-politics-brazil>

Segatto, C. I., Alves, M. A., & Pineda, A. (2023). Uncivil society and social policies in Brazil: The backlash in the gender, sexual, and reproductive rights and ethnic and racial relations fields. *Public Administration and Development*, 43(1), 60-69. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pad.1992>

Silva, E. C. de M.. TelegramScrap: A comprehensive tool for scraping Telegram data. (feb) 2023. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2412.16786>.

Stotzer, R. L., & Nelson, A. (2025). The (anti)feminism of tradwives. *Terrorism and Political Violence*, 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09546553.2025.2463588>

Vilaça, G., & d'Andréa, C. (2021). Da manosphere à machosfera: Práticas (sub)culturais masculinistas em plataformas anonimizadas. *Revista Eco-Pós*, 24(2), 410-440. <https://doi.org/10.29146/ecopos.v24i2.27703>

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Desordem informacional sobre violência de gênero e ataques contra a Lei Maria da Penha no Telegram
Nota Técnica 003.2025 - 07 de Agosto de 2025

Mário Aquino Alves (FGV); Julie Ricard (FGV/CNPq); Ergon Cugler de Moraes Silva (FGV/CNPq); Guilherme Celestino (FGV); Gabriel Rocha (FGV/CNPq); Stefanny Vitória (FGV/CNPq)

“ Por isso o homem tem que abandonar casamento e filhos e começar a ver mulher não como ser humano, mais como vaginas que falam, que só servem pra ser depósito de espermatozoides da gente. Quem embarcar em um relacionamento moderno com a mulher moderna vai acabar na sarjeta, falido, como e respondendo falsa acusação na Maria da Penha. ”

- Mensagem em grupo conspiracionista do Telegram, 07 de dezembro de 2021.

PRINCIPAIS ACHADOS

- **Crescimento recente:** Apenas nos últimos dois anos (agosto de 2023 a julho de 2025), foram identificadas 425 menções relacionadas a ataques à Lei Maria da Penha em comunidades de teorias da conspiração no Telegram. No total do período analisado (maio de 2019 a julho de 2025), esse valor foi de 681 menções relacionadas a ataques.
- **Quase 1 milhão de visualizações, com alcance massivo:** Esses conteúdos somaram 911.824 visualizações e pelo menos 8.622 compartilhamentos, alcançando uma audiência expressiva em curto intervalo de tempo.
- **Brasil Paralelo como vetor central na distribuição:** Ao menos 6% das publicações monitoradas estão diretamente associadas a conteúdos do Brasil Paralelo, que dissemina desinformação sobre a Maria da Penha e a própria lei, atacando a legitimidade e as vítimas de violência doméstica.

Redes de ódio e violência contra mulheres

Mapeamento da machosfera brasileira no Telegram e modelos de monetização

NOV/2025
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